

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES MADE BY AUTOMATED FIBER PLACEMENT

Minh Duc Hoang, Jeffrey Fortin Simpson and Suong Van Hoa

Concordia Centre for Composites
Department of Mechanical and Industrial Engineering
Concordia University

Center for Research in Polymers and Composites (CREPEC)
Montreal, Quebec, Canada
Email: hoasuon@alcor.concordia.ca

Keywords: Thermoplastic composites, Automated Fiber Placement, Manufacturing procedure, Characterization, Process parameters.

ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results of an investigation to determine the mechanical properties of flat coupons made of carbon/PEEK and using AFP. The intention is to determine whether laminates made using AFP would have similar properties as those made using proven methods such as compression moulding and autoclave. There are many challenges in making flat laminates of thermoplastic composites using AFP machine with a small deposition head, on a mold at room temperature. The laminate tends to distort during and after the process. This is due to many reasons: (i) The deformation of the composite strip as it is laid down. There is deformation in both the width and thickness directions. (ii) The relaxation of the material right after material deposition. (iii) Deformation due to cooling. (iv) Difference in expansion coefficient between the mandrel and the composite. (v) Difference in expansion and/or contraction between the layer being laid and the previously laid layers. (vi) Difference in crystallinity between the layer being laid and the previously laid layers.

In order to eliminate some of the issues mentioned above, a hot mandrel was used during the process of making the flat laminates. The mandrel is kept at above the T_g of the composite during the whole time when the material is deposited. After all layers have been deposited, the whole laminate is cooled down to room temperature. With this method, it was possible to make flat thermoplastic laminates. Microscopic observation was made on cross sections of the samples to determine void content. The laminates were subjected to tensile, compressive and shear tests. The results are compared with those obtained from samples made by autoclave. It is found that thermoplastic composites made by AFP exhibit similar or better properties than those made by autoclave.

1 INTRODUCTION

Automated Fiber Placement is a manufacturing technique that can be used for both thermoset and thermoplastic composites. Figure 1 illustrates the in-situ consolidation tow placement process. Prepreg tow is fed to roller and is heated by a hot gas torch or by a laser system up to melting temperature. For hot gas torch, the inert gas is usually nitrogen to avoid any explosion. Another role of this inert gas is to protect tows from oxidative degradation during layup process [1] [2]. Roller with or without its own heating system then lays down the tow to the substrate and applies compaction force to bond it to the substrate. Consolidation of the tows happens under transient high temperature condition. The tow is then cut to finish one tow. Afterward, the robot brings the head to a new position and starts laying the next tow. This process repeats until the designed part is built.

Figure 1: Schematic drawing of fiber placement Process

During manufacturing process, there are a few factors affect the quality of the final product. These are material properties, hot gas temperature, layup speed, compaction force of the roller, mandrel's temperature etc. The effects of individual variable or combination of some of them have been presented in many papers [3-13].

First of all is the effect of thermoplastic material properties. Different thermoplastic resins have different properties such as glass transition temperature (T_g) and melting temperature (T_m). Therefore, depending on material used for manufacturing, process window will be changed. Gruber et al. [3] concluded that material, process and head parameters have a big influence on intraply and interply void content inside laminate made by AFP with in situ consolidation. Furthermore, this paper showed that by using commercial grade thermoplastic tapes, there is not enough time at manufacturing temperatures to fully consolidate and bond tapes to substrate during in situ consolidation process. Also, some tapes lacking surface resin may not generate full layer-to-layer weld strength. Finally, by improving tape quality, laminate properties are improved. For example, Short Beam Shear Strength (SBSS) increases from 76% to 105% of the SBSS of an autoclave laminate by changing from commercial APC-2 AS4 for still-developing APC-2 AS4. APC2-AS4 prepreg which is also used in this study contains PEEK resin which is considered as semi-crystalline material [4] and the degree of crystallinity affects the properties of the final laminate [5, 6]. These papers show that the higher crystallinity laminate provides higher tensile, compression and shear modulus and strength. However, the mode I fracture toughness decreases when the degree of crystallinity increases [6]. The degree of crystallinity of thermoplastic composite depends mainly on the cooling rate [5, 7]; it decreases when the cooling rate increases. Moreover, non-uniform crystallinity in a part influences residual stress in the laminate[8].

During manufacturing process, laminate is subjected to several heating and cooling cycles which will result in residual stresses inside final laminates. These residual stresses can cause matrix cracking which can reduce the stiffness up to 35% [9] [10]. Heating and cooling are affected by many parameters such as layup speed, temperature of hot gas torch, layup sequences, ambient temperature etc. Tierney and Gillespie [11] studied the crystallization behavior of PEEK composites in different heating and cooling rate conditions. Hot gas temperature was kept at 850°C, layup speed and the distance from the torch to prepreg were varied. They found that the crystallinity along cross section of a single ply is uneven and it is affected by both speed and the distance between torch and prepreg. The low layup speed provided higher crystallinity but higher speed resulted in more even crystallinity along cross section.

Another parameter affecting residual stresses of composite laminate is tape tension. Lu et al. [12] found that the increment of tape tension has a big effect on the final residual stresses when doing filament winding. If the tape tensions are constant, radial residual stresses are tensile. In case of increasing tape tension, radial stresses are compressive. In case of decreasing tape tension, absolute value of radial and circumferential residual stresses are higher than those with constant tape tensions.

Brzeski and Schledjewski [13] showed the effect of tool temperature on laminate properties when manufacturing composite laminates by AFP with in situ consolidation. By increasing tool temperature, interlaminar shear strength increases. However, if temperature of the tool is too high, temperature of the laminate after consolidation is also too high so that deconsolidation will happen and interply adhesion

is decreased. Another conclusion from this paper is the ratio between the heat input to incoming tape and that to substrate influences residual stresses of the laminate.

2 MATERIAL

Material used is thermoplastic prepreg PEEK APC-2/AS4 distributed by CYTEC [14]. Figure 2 shows a cross section of a tow. The average thickness of prepreg tape is 0.005 in (0.127 mm). It shows clearly the variation of surface roughness along tow width. Moreover, it is noted that the roughness on two sides are different, one with high surface roughness value and the other is smoother. The smoother side has higher fiber fraction and less resin near its surface than the opposite side of the prepreg. During layup process, the rougher side of the previous ply will be in contact with the smoother side of the current ply. By flipping the prepreg tape, the smoother side can be on top and will be in contact with the rougher side of the incoming tape. From our observation, which side is up does not affect the quality of the final laminate. However, within a piece of prepreg, there are some resin rich areas, some places where fibers are in contact with others and some small amount of void. These defects may have influence on the quality of the final products.

Figure 2: Micrograph of CYTEC prepreg

3 MANUFACTURING PROCESSES

3.1 Setup

Figure 3 shows the setup for a heated mandrel. Steel plate with dimension of 30 in x 22 in x 3/8 in is used as the mandrel. Steel table was placed above radiant heater; distance from top surface of the heater to bottom surface of the table is 3 inches (76.2 mm). Surface temperature of the radiant heater can reach up to 2000°F (1095°C). Due to dimensions of heater and table, distance from edge of the heater to edge of the mandrel in one direction is 3 inches (76.2 mm), and in the other direction, that distance is also 3 inches (76.2 mm). Four legs of the table were clamped to the base to fix the table during manufacturing process. To avoid heat loss to environment, surrounding space between heater and steel table was covered by insulation panel. A thermocouple is placed at the middle of the bottom side of the mandrel and is connected to the controller for the feedback signal. In other words, the temperature of the bottom surface but not the top surface is controlled. In order to have information about surface temperature, infrared camera is used. The working area where material is laid down is at the middle of the mandrel because this area has the most uniform temperature distribution.

Figure 3: Heated Mandrel Setup

3.2 Unidirectional laminates manufacturing

Two types of unidirectional laminates were manufactured. These are $[0]_8$ laminates and $[0]_{12}$ laminates. $[0]_8$ laminates were made in order to make samples for tensile test while $[0]_{12}$ laminates were manufactured for compression test.

First ply dimensions of $[0]_8$ laminates are 11 inches (279.4 mm) long and 6 inches (152.4 mm) wide. Those of $[0]_{12}$ laminates are 7 inches x 6 inches (177.8 mm x 152.4 mm). For all plies, prepreg was laid down from left to right. Since sliding may happen when laying down material directly on top of the substrate, for subsequent layers, it was decided to extend 0.25 inch (6.4 mm) outside the edge of previous layer at the beginning and at the end. This means the prepreg will be placed down and bond to the metal substrate at the starting point. To avoid building up weak contact at band boundary, the plies are offset by half of a band.

Processing parameters for manufacturing unidirectional laminates were set as in Table 1. Temperature at the bottom of the mandrel was kept at 200°C during layup process. Temperature of Hot Gas Torch was 825°C, nitrogen flow rate was 60 SLPM, and layup speed was 0.5 in/s (0.76 m/minute) for the first ply and was increased to 1 in/s (1.52 m/minute) for the rest. Compaction force was 100 lbf. There is a difference between the process for the 12 layer laminate and the 8 layer laminate. It was noticed that the temperature of the 9th layer was too hot and the material was too soft to apply the 10th layer. Therefore, compressed air was used to reduce the surface temperature. This helps to reduce the softness of the previously laid material and to improve bonding. The reduction of surface temperature also helped to obtain better surface finish.

One repass was applied starting from 4th ply for unidirectional laminates. The moving speed of roller for repass is 2 in/s. Compaction force is kept at 100 lbf.

Parameter	$[0]_8$ laminates	$[0]_{12}$ laminates
Hot Gas Temperature	825C	825C
Layup speed	0.5 in/s (0.76 m/minute) for 1 st ply, 1 in/s (1.52 m/minute) for plies 2 nd to 8 th	0.5 in/s (0.76 m/minute) for 1 st ply, 1 in/s (1.52 m/minute) for plies 2 nd to 12 th
Compaction force	100 lbf	100 lbf
Steel plate temperature	200°C	200°C
Nitrogen Flow rate	60 SLPM	60 SLPM

Table 1: Processing parameters for unidirectional laminates

Once layup process is finished, laminates were left for natural cooling after manufacturing by turning off the heater. After cooling, the laminates were automatically released partly from mandrel. The laminates are flat (Figure 4-5), and only a small part at one edge was popped up from the surface. Furthermore, both surfaces finish on the top and bottom are good.

Figure 4: $[0]_8$ laminate after removing from mandrel

Figure 5: $[0]_{12}$ laminate after removing from mandrel

3.3 $[45/-45]_{2S}$ laminates manufacturing

$[45/-45]_{2S}$ laminates were made in order to characterize shear modulus and shear strength of the material. The required dimensions of these laminates are 11 inches x 7 inches (279.4 mm x 177.8 mm). First ply was laid down with size of 14 inches x 10 inches (355.6 mm x 254.0 mm) but the following plies have the same dimensions of 11 inches x 7 inches (279.4 mm x 177.8 mm). In other words, there is no offset of every layer to have the start point on metal mandrel. Otherwise, from the second ply of $[45/-45]_{2S}$ laminate, the starting point is right on the composite substrate. Layup direction is as shown in Figure 6. Layup direction for 45° layers is in negative x and negative y direction; layup direction for -45° layers is in positive x and negative y direction.

Figure 6: Layup direction for $[45/-45]_{2S}$ laminate

Processing parameters are presented in Table 2. Mandrel temperature was kept at 200°C during of the first two plies and then was reduced to 155°C during the layout of 3rd to 8th ply. Layup speed is 0.5 in/s (0.76 m/minute) for the first ply and is increased to 1 in/s (1.52 m/minute) for the remaining process. HGT is 825°C, nitrogen flow rate is 60 SLPM and compaction force is 100 lbs. Moreover, starting from the 3rd ply, compressed air was used to cool down the surface simultaneously in order to keep the top surface not too soft. After finishing the 8th ply, a steel caul plate which has the same dimensions as the mandrel, was placed on top of the laminate. Insulation panel was used to cover the top of the caul plate. Heated mandrel temperature was set at 200°C. Heater was left for one hour to bring temperature of the whole assembly to 200°C. Finally, heater was turned off and laminate was cooled down naturally between two caul plates.

One repress was applied starting from 3rd ply. The moving speed of roller for repress is 2 in/s. Compaction force is kept at 100 lbf.

Parameter	Value
Hot Gas Temperature	825°C
Feed rate of the Roller	0.5 in/s (0.76 m/minute) for 1 st ply, 1 in/s (1.52 m/minute) for plies 2 nd to 8 th .
Compaction force	100 lbs
Tool surface temperature	200°C for 1 st and 2 nd ply, 155°C for 3 rd to 8 th ply
Nitrogen Flow rate	60 SLPM

Table 2: Processing parameters for [45/-45]_{2S} laminate

Figure 7: [45/-45]_{2S} laminate after removing from mandrel and trimming edges

((a) Top view (b) Isometric view)

Figure 7 shows the [45/-45]_{2S} laminate after trimming the edges. The laminate is flat and there is no warpage. It is clearly seen that using a caul plate with same temperature as mandrel placing on top made cooling rate through thickness uniform. Furthermore, hot caul plate helped to reduce cooling rate of the

whole laminate so it had more time at temperature higher than T_g to release residual stresses due to cooling. The obtained laminate met requirement for testing.

4 PRELIMINARY QUALITY VERIFICATION

4.1 Microscopic observation

Figures 8-10 show respectively microscopic images for $[0]_8$, $[0]_{12}$, and $[45/-45]_{2S}$ laminates made by AFP. From those pictures, it is noted that there are defects inside laminate such as voids and resin rich areas. Resin rich areas which are found inside layers are due to prepreg quality. Resin rich areas which are located at interlayer boundaries can be explained by high surface roughness of the material. Surface roughness creates empty channels along fiber direction. When AFP head laid down a tow on substrate, it squeezed resin to fill the spaces created by surface roughness. These areas can be reached only by resin but it is difficult for fibers to go in. It is also clearly seen that there are very few interply voids. This is because of applying repass.

Figure 8: Microscopic image for $[0]_8$ laminate samples with 1 repass

Figure 9: Microscopic image for $[0]_{12}$ laminate samples with 1 repass

Figure 10: Microscopic image for $[45/-45]_{2S}$ laminate samples with 1 repass

4.2 Crystallinity

Figure 11 a, b, c show heat flow of $[0]_8$, $[0]_{12}$, and $[45/-45]_{2S}$ respectively. In all these three figures, it is noted that there is no peak representing crystallization of PEEK. In other words, the PEEK resin has reached it maximum level of crystallization.

Figure 11: Heat flow of laminate samples made by AFP

5 MECHANICAL TESTING

Tensile, compression and in-plane shear tests were performed on the MTS testing station using 100 kN load cell. Five samples are tested for each test so as to obtain a satisfactory average and change variance. Table 3 shows the test methods and standard specimen dimensions.

Test Method	Measured Property	Coupon Length/Width (in)	Stacking Sequence
ASTM D3039	Tensile Strength and Modulus	10.0/0.5	$[0]_8$
ASTM D3410	Compressive Strength and Modulus	7.0/0.5	$[0]_{12}$
ASTM 3518	Shear Strength and Modulus	10.0/1.0	$[45/-45]_{2S}$

Table 3: Standard specimen dimensions and stacking sequence[15]

6 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 12 shows the Stress-Strain curve and sample after failure of the tensile test. During testing, it is noticed that delamination happened first, then followed by fiber fracture. The failure mode and area is DGM. The first character represents for failure mode, D means *Delamination*. The second character represents for failure area, G means at *Gage*. The third character represents for failure location, M means *Middle*.

Figure 12: a) Stress vs strain curve for tensile test. b) Sample after tensile test

Figure 13 shows the Stress-Strain curve and sample after failure of the compression test. The failure mode and area is HAT. The first character represents for failure mode, H means *Through-thickness*. The second character represents for failure area, A means at *Grip/tab*. The third character represents for failure location, T means *Top*.

Figure 13: a) Stress vs strain curve for compression test. b) Sample after compression test

Figure 14 shows the Stress-Strain curve and sample after failure of the shear test.

Figure 14: a) Stress vs strain curve for shear test. b) Sample after shear test

		AFP	Autoclave (A) [16]	$\frac{AFP}{A}$
Tensile	Average value	165	136	122%
Modulus (GPa)	Standard Deviation	0.23	3.61	
	Coefficient of Variation (%)	0.14	2.66	
Tensile	Average value	2420	2446	99%
Strength (MPa)	Standard Deviation	93.09	44.34	
	Coefficient of Variation (%)	3.84	1.81	
Compressive	Average value	144	123	117%
Modulus (GPa)	Standard Deviation	7.08	0.40	
	Coefficient of Variation (%)	4.92	0.32	
Compressive	Average value	1055	1407	75%
Strength (MPa)	Standard Deviation	37.70	9.44	
	Coefficient of Variation (%)	3.57	0.67	
Shear	Average value	5.3	5.5	96%
Modulus (GPa)	Standard Deviation	0.28	0.20	
	Coefficient of Variation (%)	5.28	3.64	
Shear	Average value	101	80	120%
Strength (MPa)	Standard Deviation	4.59	1.27	
	Coefficient of Variation (%)	4.54	1.59	

Table 4: Properties of laminates made by AFP and by autoclave consolidation

Table 4 summarizes the results of tensile test coupons made by AFP. Results for samples made by compression in autoclave obtained by Cai et al. [16] are presented as reference point to compare. Tensile and compressive moduli of laminates made by AFP are higher than those made by autoclave. Increase

in tensile and compressive modulus can be explained by reduction of thickness and thus increasing in fiber volume fraction v_f . The tensile strength for laminate made by AFP is 2420 MPa, for laminate made by autoclave consolidation is 2446 MPa, the difference is 1.06% which is negligible. However, the compressive strength for laminate made by AFP (1055 MPa) is lower by 25% than laminate made by autoclave (1407 MPa). The shear modulus for laminates made by AFP (2420 MPa) is slightly lower than laminate made by autoclave (2446 MPa), the difference is 1.06%. Shear strength of laminates made by AFP is 101 MPa which is 20% higher than shear strength of laminates made by autoclave (80 MPa). However, shear strength of laminates made by autoclave was obtained with ASTM D5379[16] test while laminates made by AFP were subjected to ASTM D3518 test. The difference of test conditions may create the different results.

7 CONCLUSION

This study proposed a procedure for making flat thermoplastic laminates with different layup sequences and different thicknesses by AFP heated by a hot gas torch and simple tape deposition head. Afterward, thermoplastic laminates made by AFP with proposed parameters were characterized. Tensile, compression and in-plane shear tests were done and mechanical properties such as tensile strength and modulus, compression strength and modulus and shear strength and modulus were found. Results were then compared with those made by autoclave consolidation. Tensile modulus is higher by 22%. Tensile strength is at the same level. Compression modulus is higher by 17%. Compression strength reduces for 25%. Shear modulus is at the same level. Shear strength increases by 20% but the two tests are different so it is not a fair comparison.

The improvement in tensile modulus and compression modulus was explained by the higher fiber volume fraction of laminates made by AFP compared to those made by autoclave consolidation. Reduction of compressive strength needs further study.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The supports of NSERC Industrial Chair on Automated Composites, Bell Helicopter Textron Canada Ltd., and Bombardier Aerospace are gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

- [1] Moddeman, W.E., Bowling, W.C., Tibbitts, E.E., and Whitaker, R.B., *Thermal stability and compatibility of polyetheretherketone (PEEK) with an oxidizer and pyrotechnic blend*. Polymer Engineering & Science, 1986. **26**(21): p. 1469-1477.
- [2] Day, M., Cooney, J.D., and Wiles, D.M., *The thermal stability of poly(aryl-ether-ether-ketone) as assessed by thermogravimetry*. Journal of Applied Polymer Science, 1989. **38**(2): p. 323-337.
- [3] Mark B. Gruber, I.Z.L., Tracy L. Doland, Steven B.Funck, *Thermoplastic in situ placement requires better impregnated tapes and tows*, in *SAMPE*. 2012: Baltimore, USA.
- [4] Blundell, D.J. and Osborn, B.N., *The morphology of poly(aryl-ether-ether-ketone)*. Polymer, 1983. **24**(8): p. 953-958.
- [5] Lee, W.I., Talbott, M.F., Springer, G.S., and Berglund, L.A., *Effects of Cooling Rate on the Crystallinity and Mechanical Properties of Thermoplastic Composites*. Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites, 1987. **6**(1): p. 2-12.
- [6] Talbott, M.F., Springer, G.S., and Berglund, L.A., *The Effects of Crystallinity on the Mechanical Properties of PEEK Polymer and Graphite Fiber Reinforced PEEK*. Journal of Composite Materials, 1987. **21**(11): p. 1056-1081.
- [7] Muzzy, J.D., Bright, D.G., and Hoyos, G.H., *Solidification of poly(ethylene terephthalate) with incomplete crystallization*. Polymer Engineering & Science, 1978. **18**(6): p. 437-442.
- [8] Lee, K. and Weitsman, Y., *Effects of Nonuniform Crystallinity on Stress Distributions in Cross-Ply Graphite/PEEK (APC-2) Laminates*. Journal of Composite Materials, 1991. **25**(9): p. 1143-1157.

- [9] Kwon, Y.W. and Berner, J.M., *Matrix damage of fibrous composites: Effects of thermal residual stresses and layer sequences*. Computers & Structures, 1997. **64**(1–4): p. 375-382.
- [10] Zhang, Y., Xia, Z., and Ellyin, F., *Evolution and influence of residual stresses/strains of fiber reinforced laminates*. Composites Science and Technology, 2004. **64**(10–11): p. 1613-1621.
- [11] Tierney, J.J., Gillespie Jr, J. W., *Crystallization kinetics behavior of PEEK based composites exposed to high heating and cooling rates*. Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2004. **35**(5): p. 547-558.
- [12] Lu, H., Schlottermuller, M., Himmel, N., and Schledjewski, R., *Effects of Tape Tension on Residual Stress in Thermoplastic Composite Filament Winding*. Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials, 2005. **18**(6): p. 469-487.
- [13] M. Brzeski, R.H., R. Schledjewski, *Effect of tool temperature on laminate properties during in situ consolidation placement process*, in SAMPE. 2010: Seattle, USA.
- [14] *APC-2 PEEK thermoplastic polymer Technical Data Sheet*, http://www.cyttec.com/sites/default/files/datasheets/APC-2_PEEK_031912-01.pdf.
- [15] *Annual book of ASTM standards 2010*, ed. West Conshohocken, PA: ASTM International, 2010.
- [16] Cai, X., *Determination of Process Parameters for the Manufacturing of Thermoplastic Composite Cones Using Automated Fiber Placement*. Master Thesis, 2012, Concordia.